

COFFEE CAPSULES

DO YOU KNOW?

The global **coffee capsule** market is estimated at 80 billion unit. The industry is experiencing a major shift as **sustainability and environmental awareness** take center stage.

Growing consumer demand for specialty and organic coffee pods is driving the market, highlighting a shift toward premium and sustainably sourced products. Under the European Union's Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), coffee and tea capsules will continue to be recognized as a valid packaging solution, provided they meet certain requirements — including being **compostable**.

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop compostable coffee capsules that are not only sustainable but also with enhanced barrier properties and functionality. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Biodegradability and Compostability** – Certified for industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)
- **Recyclability of the bioplastics** – Available for injection moulded packaging in bioplastic non contaminated by organic waste
- **Lower Carbon Footprint** – Over 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to traditional plastic capsules
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion
- **Improved oxygen barrier**

How it works?

TERRIFIC coffee capsules will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be then converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers**, which can then be shaped into capsules using conventional manufacturing techniques such as injection moulding.

What can I do?

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FLEXIBLE FILM PACKAGING

DO YOU KNOW?

As environmental awareness grows, there is a rising demand for **sustainable and biodegradable flexible films**.

So, the market for sustainable flexible films is expected to grow as both consumers and industries increasingly **prioritize sustainable materials**.

According to the PPWR*, these applications are included in the list of products for which member states may allow their marketability if compostable.

* European Union's Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop biobased and biodegradable film packaging for crispy snacks. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Biodegradability and Compostability** – Certified for both industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)
- **Material Reusability:** Ensure the recycling feasibility to re-use the material through repulping processes
- **Lower Carbon Footprint** – Over 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to traditional plastic
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion
- **Improved moisture and oxygen barrier properties**

How it works?

TERRIFIC flexible film packaging will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers**, which are then combined with **FSC® Control Wood Standard-certified paper**.

Conventional manufacturing technologies, such as film blowing, barrier coating, paper lamination and extrusion coating will be used to convert it into flexible film packaging.

What can I do?

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STICK PACKS

DO YOU KNOW?

The **stick packaging** industry is poised for significant growth, with its value expected to increase from USD 1,452.6 million in 2025 to USD 2,277.5 million by 2035, driven by increasing consumer demand for **convenient, sustainable, and innovative packaging** solutions across the food, beverage, and health sectors.

However, **the rise of single-use stick packs is contributing to significant waste**, as many are non-recyclable **due to material mixing and contamination**, leading to increased landfill and environmental pollution.

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop biobased, biodegradable, compostable and repulpable stick pack for nutraceuticals. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Biodegradability and Compostability** – Certified for industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)
- **Additional end of life** – Possibility to dispose the packaging in paper waste stream due to the compatibility of the material and product with repulping processes, recovering the cellulosic fibers
- **Lower Carbon Footprint** – Over 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to the traditional plastic
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion
- **Improved moisture and oxygen barrier properties**

How it works?

TERRIFIC stick packs will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers** and combined with **FSC® Control Wood Standard-certified paper**. Conventional manufacturing technologies, such as film blowing and paper lamination, will be used to convert it into **compostable and repulpable barrier stick packs**.

What can I do?

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EXPANDED THERMOBOXES FOR FROZEN LOOSE FOOD

DO YOU KNOW?

The **cold chain packaging market** is projected to reach USD 70.4 billion by 2032, driven by the increasing demand for temperature-sensitive products. The sector is evolving with technological advancements aimed at enhancing efficiency, reducing waste, and increasing sustainability.

There is an interest in investing in **innovative materials** designed to develop **reusable, recyclable, and biodegradable packaging solutions** while ensuring optimal performance and minimal environmental impact.

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop biobased reusable, recyclable and biodegradable expanded thermoboxes. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Reusability:** the re-usability of the boxes is guaranteed by functionality and ecodesign of the packaging solution
- **Recyclability:** Biomaterials can be recycled at the end of the thermobox's lifecycle
- **Biodegradability and Compostability** of the barrier flagship packaging solution – Certified for both industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion
- **Potential for replication in expanded products with high probability of microplastic**

How it works?

TERRIFIC expanded thermoboxes for frozen loose food will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers**, which can then be shaped into expanded thermoboxes using conventional manufacturing techniques such as beads and microbeads foaming.

What can I do?

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FOOD TRAYS

DO YOU KNOW?

The global **food trays** market was valued at USD 10.84 billion in 2024 and is expected to grow from USD 11.40 billion in 2025 to USD 17.99 billion by 2034. A key trend in the food tray market is the rising demand for **sustainable packaging solutions**. As consumers become more environmentally conscious, there is a noticeable shift toward sustainable materials. This change not only reflects **growing preferences for biodegradable and recyclable materials** but also addresses concerns about the **environmental impact of packaging**, making it a vital factor in the food tray market. According to the PPWR*, these applications are included in the list of products for which member states may allow their marketability if compostable.

* European Union's Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop biobased and biodegradable trays for meat and dairy products. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Biodegradability and Compostability** – Certified for both industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)
- **Additional end of life** – Possibility to dispose the packaging in paper waste stream due to the compatibility of the material and product with repulping processes, recovering the cellulosic fibers
- **Lower Carbon Footprint** – Over 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to traditional plastic
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion
- **Improved moisture and oxygen barrier properties**

How it works?

TERRIFIC food trays will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers**, which are then combined with **FSC® Control Wood Standard-certified pulp**. Conventional manufacturing technologies, such as film blowing, multilayer structure and pulp thermolamination, will be used to convert it into compostable and repulpable barrier tray packs.

What can I do?

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AIR BUBBLE FILMS

DO YOU KNOW?

The global **air bubble film** market was valued at around USD 2.5 billion in 2023 and is forecast to reach around USD 4.1 billion by 2032.

This growth is driven by the **increasing demand for protective packaging solutions** across various industries, as air bubble films provide superior cushioning and shock absorption.

The market is evolving with advances in materials science leading to the development of more durable and environmentally friendly solutions.

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop reusable and recyclable air cushioning and bubble film. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Biodegradability & Compostability:** Certified for industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)
- **Reusability:** Designed for multiple uses before disposal
- **Recyclability:** Made from materials that can be reintroduced into recycling streams
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion

How it works?

TERRIFIC Air Bubble Films will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers**, which can then be shaped into Air Bubble Films using a combination of technologies such as film blowing and bubble thermoforming.

What can I do?

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BIO-BASED YOGURT CUPS

DO YOU KNOW?

The EU produces approximately 7.69 million tons of yogurt each year, usually packaged in multi-material containers that complicate the recycling process.

As consumers become more environmentally conscious, demand for sustainable yogurt packaging is rising.

There is a growing preference for sustainable materials that reduce the product's overall environmental impact, **making sustainable packaging solutions a key market trend in the coming years.**

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop biobased compostable and recyclable thermoformed cups for yogurt and dairy products. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Biodegradability and Compostability** – Certified for both industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)
- **Recyclability of the bioplastics:** available for thermoformed packaging for bioplastic non contaminated by organic waste.
- **Lower Carbon Footprint** – Over 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to traditional plastic
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion
- **Improved moisture barrier properties**

How it works?

TERRIFIC yogurt cups will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers**, which can then be shaped into cups combining technologies such as multi-layer sheet extrusion and thermoforming.

WHY? to offer more sustainable cups for yogurt and dairy products that could be disposed with organic waste, **ensuring food safety and improving circularity.**

What can I do?

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WOVEN TEA BAGS

DO YOU KNOW?

Millions of tons of **tea bag** waste are generated annually. Sustainability is a **key factor in the tea bag market**. Many manufacturers now offer **biodegradable and compostable materials** in response to growing environmental concerns. This trend aligns with consumer demand for environmentally friendly packaging, further supporting market growth. Manufacturers that prioritize innovation in **sustainable packaging, flavor and materials are expected to gain a significant position in this market**.

As sustainability becomes a key priority in the tea market, manufacturers are increasingly shifting towards biodegradable and compostable materials. This shift is driven by **consumer demand for eco-friendly alternatives** and presents a **growth opportunity** for brands that innovate in **sustainable packaging, materials, and product quality**.

TERRIFIC SOLUTION

What is it? TERRIFIC will develop biobased and compostable woven tea bags. They will be designed to work with various end-of-life options.

Challenges & Environmental Benefit: TERRIFIC goals

- **Biodegradability & Compostability:** Certified for **industrial and home composting (OK COMPOST)**
- **Lower Carbon Footprint** – Over 50% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to the traditional plastic
- **Does not release persistent microplastics** into the environment, even in case of accidental dispersion

How it works?

TERRIFIC tea bag waste will be made from over **95% renewable resources**, including used cooking oils and agro-industry sugar residues. These materials will be converted into **biodegradable and recyclable biopolymers**, which can then be shaped into tea bags combining technologies such as melt spinning and weaving.

WHY: to offer a sustainable tea bags that could be composted accordingly to the PPWR* while maintaining tea quality and flavor release.

* European Union's Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWRR)

What can I do?

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